

Supplementary Fig. 3E

PANC-1

shControl
shp110δ #1
shp110δ #2

250
130
95

Rabbit monoclonal Anti-p110 δ (E2T2N) + anti-rabbit HRP (ECL)

55

Rabbit monoclonal Anti-Phospho-AKT (Ser473) (D9E) + anti-rabbit HRP (ECL)

72

55

36

Mouse monoclonal Anti-AKT (pan) (40D4) + anti-mouse IRDye 800 CW

72

55

36

Mouse monoclonal Anti- α -tubulin + anti-mouse IRDye 800 CW